

University Marine Energy Research Community

2023 Conference

4-6 October | Durham, NH, USA

Spectral Response of a Horizontal Axis Tidal Turbine Subjected to Grid Turbulence

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Abstract

The conversion dynamics from velocity fluctuations to turbine power must be better understood for optimal blade design and control, which may transfer intermittency in the electrical grid for a tidal farm, creating a need for expensive control devices. In this context, the spectral response of a 1:20 scaled tidal turbine (compared to a full-scale 5m turbine) subjected to freestream grid turbulence in a water tunnel is studied. The water tunnel facility has a cross-section of 0.61m x 0.61m and 2m in length, offering a solid blockage of 16.5% in the presence of a turbine. The test facility has an inflow velocity of 0.83m/s and is equipped with an active grid turbulence generator generating turbulence intensity around 12-14% at the rotor plane. The turbine is controlled using a constant-speed stepper motor with an embedded torque sensor. We investigate the influence of tip-speed ratios TSR (1-6), elevated turbulence, integral length scale, and periodic structures on turbine power spectra. Four inflow conditions are tested: quasi-laminar (no grid), two elevated-turbulence cases with the difference being in integral length scales, and the synchronous case having periodic structures at grid frequency (also higher harmonics) and elevated turbulence. We identify three distinct regions for all cases: low-frequency regime, which directly scales with inflow; an intermediate region where quasi-laminar shows f^{-2} decay, whereas, for elevated turbulence, an increase in tip-speed ratio resulted in clear low-pass filtering exhibiting the $f^{-11/3}$ ($f^{-2}f^{-5/3}$) decay law. However, for a larger integral length/time scale, the turbine shows an exciting transition from $f^{-5/3}$ at lower TSR to $f^{-8/3}$ region for higher TSR, shifting the decay to lower frequencies. The change is likely due to the rotor inertial time scale (increasing with TSR) dominating the impact of the larger time scale from the inflow. The high-frequency regime is infiltrated with peaks corresponding to rotor frequency and higher harmonics. Moreover, the turbine spectra indicated strong signatures of the impact of periodic structures, which may enhance the fatigue loading of the blades.

Keywords: Tidal turbine; Power spectra; Fluid-structure interactions

1. Introduction

Tidal energy represents a significant opportunity to increase the world's renewable power generation capacity [1]. Tides are more predictable and may offset the intermittency issues of solar and wind [2]. However, tidal turbines operate in a highly turbulent flow, requiring stronger structures than their wind turbine counterpart [3]. Further, these velocity fluctuations impart intermittency in the turbine power output, which is detrimental to turbine fatigue life and requires control devices/synchronizers for stabilizing the grid [4]. The learnings from wind energy cannot be directly mapped owing to the higher turbulence in the tidal flows. Therefore, there is a need to understand the aggregate and

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scale-to-scale interaction of the different inflow conditions to the turbine output. In this study, we discuss controlled laboratory experiments mimicking the tidal site conditions in a laboratory water tunnel to quantify the impact of turbulent inflow on the turbine power output in the frequency domain using the Fourier Transform. The study allows us to decouple the effects of elevated turbulence, integral length scales (ILS), periodic/coherent structures, and tip-speed ratios (TSR) on turbine power output and broaden our understanding of the conversion dynamics from velocity fluctuations to turbine power fluctuations. Further, it will help turbine developers optimize the design of the rotor blades and identify optimal operating conditions of tidal energy converters.

2. Methodology

2.1. Tidal turbine specifications and testing facility

The experiments were conducted in an open surface, recirculating water tunnel called the Tidal Turbulence Testing Facility (T³F) [3] at Lehigh University (Bethlehem, PA). A three-bladed 1:20 model scaled tidal turbine (compared to full-scale 5m turbine) having SG6043 profile, constant chord, and no twist blades [3] is used, as shown in Figure 1(a). The rotor and shaft assembly are connected with a stepper motor, which maintains the constant angular speed (Ω). The rotor plane is at $2D$ (D is the turbine diameter) from the test section inlet, and the embedded torque/thrust sensors have a 200Hz sampling frequency. All experiments reported in this study were conducted at a freestream velocity (U_∞) of 0.83m/s, corresponding to the Reynolds number based on a turbine diameter 2.2×10^5 . The setup offers a solid blockage of 16.5% in presence of turbine and so the turbine performance data is corrected for blockage based on methodology used Bahaj *et al.*[5]

Fig. 1. Schematic of (a) tidal turbine assembly; (b) Water tunnel (T³F) equipped with a Makita-type [3] active grid; (c) Active grid used; (d) forcing protocol for active grid Double Random (DR) and Synchronous (SY).

2.2. Turbulence generation and inflow characterization

The water tunnel is equipped with a Makita-type active grid [3] to generate freestream turbulence, as shown in Figure 1(b). We perform simultaneous flow and turbine measurements for a period of $T=120$ s. Four inflow conditions are used: quasi-laminar (QL) (no grid), elevated turbulence cases DR025 and DR1, with the former having a larger integral length scale, and SY025 having periodic structures and elevated turbulence. For DR025 and DR1, the grid is operated in double random (DR) mode [3] (shaft rotation and direction both randomized) with a maximum frequency of 0.25Hz and 1Hz, respectively. Similarly, for SY025, the grid operates in synchronous (SY) mode having a fixed frequency of 0.25Hz with adjacent shafts of an active grid moving in opposite directions. The instantaneous streamwise velocity $\mathbf{u}(t)$ is then decomposed into the time-averaged mean (\mathbf{U}) and fluctuations $[\mathbf{u}'(t)]$, which is used to calculate the turbulence intensity (Ti), and integral length scale (L) as

$$Ti = \sqrt{u'^2} / U; \quad L = U \int_0^T \frac{\overline{u'(t)u'(t+\tau)}}{\overline{u'^2(t)}} d\tau; \quad (1)$$

Table 1 presents the measured turbulence statistics for all test cases used for this study. The DR025 has $L\sim O(D)$, though similar Ti as DR1 and SY025. Further, the power spectral density (PSD) is shown in Figure 2, which depicts the presence of periodic structures corresponding to the grid frequency (0.25Hz) and its higher harmonics for SY025. As expected, the $-5/3$ slope in elevated- Ti cases is absent for the QL case.

Table 1. Flow statistics were measured using an Acoustic Doppler Velocimeter (ADV) at 1D upstream of the rotor

Protocols/ Cases	QL	DR025	DR1	SY025
Ti (%)	1.514	18.767	16.729	16.451
L/D	0.292	0.809	0.212	0.170

Fig. 2. PSD vs. frequency of the inflow velocity measured for optimum TSR ($\lambda = \Omega D / 2U_\infty$) where D is the turbine diameter. The SY025 is vertically shifted up by a decade for clarity.

3. Results

The interaction between the temporal flow field and turbine blades generates lift and drag forces responsible for instantaneous rotor torque $Q(t)$ measured using embedded sensors, which is used to calculate power $P(t) = Q(t)\Omega$. However, we can also calculate turbine power using the disk-average relation with the power coefficient C_p given as $P(t) = (1/2)\rho A C_p u^3(t)$, A is the rotor area. The latter is suitable for capturing large-scale conversion dynamics, which fails to include the effect of small-scale fluctuations and spectral filtering in the inertial subrange, as shown in Figure 3(a). The deviation from a $-5/3$ slope to a $-11/3$ slope in torque-based power output is ascribed to the rotational dynamics, which contribute to a -2 slope and is not captured in disk-averaged power. In Figure 4(b), the shaft-only PSD shows f^{-2} decay without inflow, while the motor test was found to have almost flat spectra.

Fig. 3. (a) PSD based on measured torque and estimated from disk-averaged velocity; (b) Shaft-only PSD against frequency.

3.1. Effect of elevated turbulence and tip-speed ratios

To further corroborate the presence of a -2 slope, Figure 4(a) shows PSD for the QL case at different tip-speed ratios. The amplitude at lower frequencies increases with TSR, as do the peaks at turbine frequency marked with an arrow. For elevated turbulence case DR1 [see Figure 4(b)], the decay shifts to a steeper slope of $-11/3$ ($f^{-2}f^{-5/3}$), although the peaks are damped in the presence of elevated turbulence. Interestingly, the initiation of low-pass filtering starts nearly at the same frequency $f_{low-pass} \approx 0.5U_\infty/D$. Similar findings have been reported by Deskos *et al.* [6] using their semi-analytical model since their calculations were based on the simplifying assumption of the constant chord blade profile, which we have used in our experiments. It can be argued that this behavior depends on U_∞ and D . Perhaps this is why low-pass filtering generally coincides with the beginning of the inertial subrange for the incoming flows, provided the $L/D \ll 1$.

Fig. 4. (a) Turbine PSD for QL inflow; (b) for DR1 at different TSRs. The inset shows velocity spectra measured 1D upstream of the rotor.

3.2. Effect of integral length scale and periodic structures

The higher ILS affects both the low and mid-frequency regions of the turbine power spectra (see Figure 5(a)). Likewise, an increase in spectral amplitude is observed for low frequency ($fD/U_\infty \leq 0.2$), where it exceeds the DR1, while the amplitude drops in the range of $0.2 \leq fD/U_\infty \leq 0.9$. However, contrary to theoretical results by Deskos *et al.* [6], showing a $-5/3$ slope in the lower end of the inertial subrange even for higher λ when $L/D \geq 1$, we observe DR025 shows a slope much closer to $-8/3$ instead of $-5/3$ at higher TSR operating conditions. This is further highlighted in Figure 6(a) for DR025 case where a transition from $-5/3$ to $-8/3$ is shown. Additionally, we ran experiment by creating integral length scale higher than DR025 represented by DR01. This case produced integral length scale of order of $1.5D$ with similar Ti measured 1D upstream of the turbine. The corresponding turbine PSD is shown in Figure 6(b) to further corroborate the transition. We expect the transition due to increasing inertial time scale of the turbine system with TSR dominating the spectra compare to integral length scale at lower TSR.

Fig. 5. (a) Turbine PSD for DR1, DR025, and QL case for $\lambda = 6.0$; (b) SY025 cases shown for two different λ with inset velocity spectra.

Meanwhile, in the presence of periodic structures [see Figure 5(b)], the turbine shows peaks at grid frequency (0.25Hz) and higher harmonics, indicating a strong influence of the inflow structures in modulating the turbine power output. The contribution to the total r.m.s power increases from these periodic structures with TSR. The SY025 also shows a low-pass filtering region having a $-11/3$ slope, which is more clearly developed for higher tip-speed ratios.

Fig. 6. (a) Turbine PSD vs. reduced frequency for different tip-speed ratios. (a) DR025, and (b) double random protocol with a maximum grid frequency of 0.1Hz, generating $Lu/D = 1.5$ and $Ti = 16.98\%$ for the same inflow speed measured 1D upstream of the rotor plane.

3.3. Comparison with the existing turbine power spectral models

The existing analytical/semi-analytical models by Deskos *et al.* [6] and Tobin *et al.* [7] are compared with the experimental results for DR1 and DR025, as shown in Figure 7. For $\lambda = 6.0$, both models reproduce the low-frequency regions of the turbine power spectra. For $\lambda = 3.1$, only the Deskos model works as it accounts for blade hydrodynamics through the lift-coefficient slope, which switches between 2π and 1.5 for pre and post-stall angle of attacks, whereas Tobin's model is based on the power coefficient. Further, the Deskos model also accounts for spectral amplifications towards the high-frequency end, showing peaks at blade passing frequency ($3f_T$) and higher harmonics. However, the peaks are over-predicted, which is an inherent limitation of the model since it is based on lift-force linearization, which fails to capture the small-scale turbulence interactions with the hydrodynamics of the blades.

Fig. 7. (a) PSD vs. reduced frequency for DR1; (b) DR025, the green color represents $\lambda = 3.1$ and blue for $\lambda = 6.0$

4. Conclusions

This work examined the interaction between onset turbulence and turbine power fluctuations for different tip-speed ratios. The turbine spectral response shows three distinct regions: low, intermediate, and high-frequency regions, irrespective of the inflow conditions. The low-frequency regions show direct conversion from $\mathbf{u} \rightarrow \mathbf{P}$ with amplitude increasing with λ , while the inflow and rotational dynamics strongly control the shape of the intermediate region. The

higher ILS extends the low-pass filtering regime to lower frequencies with an additional $-8/3$ slope region at higher TSR. The turbine also shows signatures of periodic structures, highlighting the strong turbulence-turbine interaction whose contribution to the r.m.s value increases with TSR. The presence of low-frequency periodic structures in the flow increases the power fluctuations, thereby enhancing the fatigue loading of the blades. Further, the existing models reproduce the low and intermediate regions but need to account for periodic/coherent structures since the Von Kármán turbulence spectrum in these models cannot capture the periodicities in the inflow.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support from the United States National Science Foundation (NSF) through Grant No.1706358 (CBET Fluid Dynamics)

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